

NATIONAL CULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF ALLUSIONS

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Abstract. This article is devoted to illustrate how cultural peculiarities can be seen with the means of stylistic device allusion. Cultural features will be shown by linguoculturemes functioning allusive meaning.

Keywords: intertextuality, linguocultreme, phraseology, antonomasia, anthroponyms, metaphor.

National and cultural peculiarities are represented in literature frequently as it comprises several types of knowledge structure that are readily available in human background knowledge and their awareness. While analyzing national cultural specificity, there is a need to mention the term linguocultureme and how it reflects cultural or national features. The science itself is called Linguoculturology which deals with linguocultural units (linguoculturemes), cultural concepts, cultural values, cultural universals, linguistic and national world pictures. The unit of this science is called linguocultureme which is a basic unit which conveys cultural information. There are different works and approaches to this notion and some prominent works are done by V.V.Vorobyov, V.A.Maslova, V.I.Karasik and others. The studies suggest that linguocultureme has several sources that can clearly illustrate culture and nation and they are verbalized in different ways. The following diagram will illustrate these features in schema.

In the diagram we can see allusion and it clarifies the relation between cultural values and their verbalization via allusion. Here the need to analyze allusion and linguocultures will arise. The diagram illustrates some verbalization means for linguocultures and we distinguished some of them that can have an allusive feature.

Here is an example for both English and Uzbek cultural specificity that can be compared according to cultural aspects that is reflected. One is Robin Hood for English literature and Alpomish for Uzbek. In English literature, Robin Hood represents characteristics of gentleman and a symbol of justice, his appearance and dressing are recognized at first sight for those in this culture and some other cultures as this character has become popular thanks to globalization. Alpomish, on the other hand, is frequently referred character in literature in the topic of courage, defending country and strong. His appearance and dressing differ from that of Robin Hood, which clearly showcases cultural peculiarities.

Here from the diagrammatic analysis, it is clear that both folklore characters are distinguished according to some peculiarities of culture and there is a common feature which is their weapon due to the time period is close that they appeared.

And now initially, we will analyze phraseological units that have allusive feature. Phraseological units are stable word groups with partially or fully transferred meaning according to the description of Kunin.[1] Stable word groups can have allusive features in it as their origin goes back to history and their creation has a strong relation to life experience and cultural development. So, in the following paragraphs we will analyze allusive phraseological units in both languages according to their culturally enriched origin. They evoke different knowledge structures, which commonly illustrates culture in reader's mind and integrate it into the comprehension process. For example, let's take a phraseological unit in Uzbek language which means to save up and keep carefully "tishining kovagida saqlamoq".[2] This phraseological unit originally goes back to religious stories, so there is cultural barrier that will appear for those from another religious background. It is the meaning that strengthened the story behind it as this was done by prophets and it integrates responsibility and seriousness to the meaning of the phraseological unit. This sample can be seen in literature in the novel titled "Oltin vodiyan shabadalar" by Oybek:

Lekin bir iloj qilib tishimda saqlayman uni.[3]

Here the meaning of phraseological unit is kept defining carefulness and responsibility.

There are other examples from Uzbek literature that has an allusive feature which illustrates cultural features:

Otang temirchi o'tmagan edi-ku, tuppa-tuzuk cho'pon edi. *Birovning mushugini "pisht" demas edi.[4]*

“Mushugini “pisht” demaslik” refers to the story that prophet loved cats and never disturbed it. This story becomes the origin of this phrase and meaning not bothering others and not harming them.

The other phraseological unit is “Daqyunusdan beri/daqyunusdan qolgan” which means very old and ancient. This was used in Askad Mukhtar’s novel “Opa-singillar”:

Daqyunusdan beri shu turishi-turish.[5]

The origin goes back to mythology, Daqyunus was one of the emperors in Rome and it is so common and popular in Eastern culture as a linguocultureme as many ancient cities in Khorezm are thought to be built in his rein.[6]

The following example is from Oybek’s novel “Oltin vodiyan shabadalar”:

Men bunday masalada alifni tayoq deyolmayman, ammo injenerlarga ishonaman.[7]

This refers to old Uzbek alphabet which began with “alif” and it means you are illiterate if you do not know even alif which is the first letter of the alphabet. Moreover, there is a reference to its shape as stake.[8] This allusive phraseological unit belongs to historical knowledge structure and historical aspects of the nation which is quite familiar to those who belong to it.

Now another example will be drawn from English literature from the novel “Cry, the Beloved Country” by Alan Paton. Here’s an excerpt from the novel that directly uses the Good Samaritan as an allusion:

"He was a stranger in the land, and he had shown him the kindness of a Good Samaritan; he had never forgotten it."

In this novel, the theme of compassion and helping those in need is central, and the reference to the *Good Samaritan* is used to highlight acts of kindness and mercy amidst the social and racial injustices faced by the characters. Here we can see how religious aspects reflected in linguoculturemes can differ according to religious background which is quite different and distinguishable.

The other phraseological units as samples are as follows:

"Maybe you should always be looking. In every box, even in every box you knew wasn't going to be anything in it. Maybe that's what it is, not knowing, all the time. Not ever knowing what comes next. But you don't ever know. Even when you think you do. You really don't." "What if I said that he's a box and I'm a box and we're both inside another box and we're watching ourselves from the box we're in. And that box is inside another box?" "Like Pandora's box."[9]

In this scene, the reference to Pandora's Box alludes to the idea of hope and despair intertwined within the journey of the characters. The allusion underscores the thematic exploration of uncertainty, curiosity, and the unforeseen consequences of human actions. This phraseological unit has a root in Greek mythology in which this box is described as evils flew out of it and only hope remained in it.[10]

The novel titled “The Godfather” by Mario Puzo will illustrate historical allusion in the form of phraseological unit. This phrase is used to signify a point of no return, much like Julius Caesar's historic crossing of the Rubicon River, which marked the start of a war.[11] This phraseological unit means deciding and not returning back:

"Michael knew that the moment had come to cross the Rubicon. There was no turning back now. The decision he made would change everything, for better or worse."

This excerpt captures the pivotal moment when Michael Corleone decides to take decisive action, signifying a major turning point in the narrative and his life, aligning with the historical reference of crossing the Rubicon.

From the analysis above it can be seen that phraseological units mainly illustrate religious aspects of culture while it is different including myths, history and religion in English.

The further analysis will take allusive antonomasia into account to show cultural aspects that will be illustrated with them. Formerly, we will define the stylistic device antonomasia and its verbalization. Antonomasia is a stylistic device that replaces person's names with descriptive phrases and turns common nouns into proper names. Not all antonomasia is allusive. For example, in Harry Potter Series by J.K.Rowling Voldemort is described as "*You-Know-Who*" or "*He-Must-Not-Be-Named*". This enriches the effect of this phrase and gives scaring atmosphere to the readers. In Uzbek language we can see this antonomasia in the sample of "*Padarkush*" which describes Abdullatif in "*Mirzo Ulug'bek*" by Maksud Shaykhzoda and "*Ulug'bek xazinas*" by Odil Yakubov. When we integrate allusion to it, it will empower literary effect and emphasis a lot.

Here we will discuss allusive antonomasia which has reference to the sources outside the precedent text. These antonomasia samples along with allusion will showcase us how cultural values can be represented by them. The following example is from Uzbek literature:

*Uchib keldim uyimga omon,
Beshyogochda gullabdi o'rik...
Toshkentga qiz berm, Marg'ilon
Qodiriy yo'q, Zaynablar tirik.[12]*

In this poem we can see that proper noun is transferred to common noun and it has a literary origin that can illustrate what is being mentioned with these names and it requires to refer to the work of Abdulla Kodiriy and the plot in it to describe the characters whose names were mentioned. Here in these lines those who are aware of this work can easily understand that here Kodiriy is the writer who decides what happens and now he is absent and it is not controlled while Zaynab is a person who poisoned Kumush and here it is the symbol of jealousy and is represented as a potential risk. Here natural value of literary work is being emphasized as a source of traditions that are described in the novel.

The following examples goes to English literature which applies antonomasia with allusive feature as a representation of cultural aspects. One poem that features allusive proper noun antonomasia from English literature is "Ode to a Nightingale" by John Keats. In this poem, Keats uses allusions to Greek mythology and literature, including the figure of Ruth, to enrich the imagery and themes. Here's a fragment from the poem:

*"Thou was not born for death, immortal Bird!
No hungry generations tread thee down;
The voice I hear this passing night was heard
In ancient days by emperor and clown:
Perhaps the self-same song that found a path
Through the sad heart of Ruth, when, sick for home,
She stood in tears amid the alien corn;
The same that oft-times hath
Charmed magic casements, opening on the foam
Of perilous seas, in faery lands forlorn."*

In this fragment, the mention of "Ruth" is an allusion to the biblical figure from the Old Testament, known for her loyalty and devotion. Keats draws on the story of Ruth standing amidst the "alien corn" to evoke themes of longing, displacement, and the transcendent power of the nightingale's song. By alluding to Ruth, Keats enriches the emotional resonance of the poem, tapping into a deep well of cultural and literary associations. This employment of allusive proper noun antonomasia enhances the poem's depth and complexity, inviting readers to engage with layers of meaning beyond the surface narrative.

One interesting thing is that both languages can provide allusive antonomasia in the form of phraseological unit. For example, in Uzbek literature "Xizrni yo'qlasam bo'larkan" means wishing to see someone really and seeing this person suddenly. This originally goes back to the story about Xizr who was supposed to be alive forever and appear suddenly.[13] This allusive expression shows religious beliefs of the nation and in literature the following fragment can be seen:

"Oldingizga kirib, maslahat olmoqchi edim. Iqbolimga o'zingiz uchrab qoldingiz. Xizrni yo'qlasam bo'larkan"[14]

This sample illustrates that there is a strong connection with religion in Uzbek allusions.

The further example is provided from English literature and allusive antonomasia in the form of a phraseological unit "sword of Damocles" can be found in Alexandre Dumas' novel "The Count of Monte Cristo." In the novel, the protagonist, Edmond Dantès, seeks revenge against those who wronged him and ultimately becomes a powerful and wealthy figure known as the Count of Monte Cristo.

In one scene, the Count converses with the villainous Baron Danglars, who is envious of the Count's wealth and status. The Count subtly reminds Danglars of the precariousness of his own position by mentioning the "sword of Damocles." Here's an excerpt from the conversation:

"But, really, by the leave of M. de Monte Cristo's great fortune, I must say that, considering the time, the day, and the circumstances, he has been rather fortunate, if I may say so."

"Yes, yes," said Monte Cristo, smiling; "but I have had no sword of Damocles hanging over me, so I should have seen everything more distinctly."[15]

In a moral anecdote in ancient Greek literature, the story tells that Damocles, a courtier to the king of Syracuse, envies the king's luxurious life and power. To teach Damocles a lesson about the precariousness of power and the constant threat of danger, the king allows him to sit on the throne with a sword suspended above him by a single hair.

Now we will turn to metaphors that has allusive characteristics and their value in illustrating culture. In George Eliot's novel "Middlemarch," the phrase "dog in the manger" is directly used. Here's an excerpt:

"If she doesn't like me, let her say so, and I'm a man who can put up with being hated. I don't make much out about being loved. But I won't be made a fool of, whether it's by man or woman. I'm not going to put up with this, and that's short and plain; and if there's anybody who thinks he can frighten me, or coax me either, let him try. I'm not a dog in a manger."

Here, the character is expressing his refusal to be manipulated or controlled by someone else's desires or actions, likening himself to a "dog in a manger" who refuses to let others enjoy what he himself cannot have. And this allusive phrase is represented with phraseological unit and it is used as a metaphor. The reason why it is allusive goes back to the story about it. From a Greek fable about a dog preventing other animals from eating the hay in a manger, even though as a

carnivore it could not eat the hay itself. Although the story was ascribed to Aesop's Fables in the 15th century, no ancient source does so. The phrase first appears in the writings of Diogenianus.[16]

Now we will analyze this in Uzbek literature. In Uzbek literature poetic genres are very common with these characters, so allusive metaphor is used mostly in poems. The following fragment will provide it:

*O'g'lim, desang osmonlarga
G'iro't bo'lib uchgayman,
Chambil yurtda Alpomishga
Navkar bo'lib tushgayman,
Padarkushdan pana qilib
Ulug'beking quchgayman,
G'ichir-g'ichir tishimdagi
So'lig'imsan, Vatanim...[17]*

Muhammad Yusuf in his poem "Vatanim" will describe himself as a horse which belonged to Alpomish who is considered, as mentioned above, very popular character that fought for the defense of the country.

From the analysis in this chapter it can be inferred that cultural values are represented via linguoculturemes and their verbalization is achieved in different ways. There are some devices of these verbalizing means which has allusive features. This in turn illustrates that allusion can serve as a means that showcases national cultural specificity.

Summary

In conceptual analysis allusion plays an important role, and precedent and recipient texts can be put parallel in some points of the concept and distinguishable in the others. Concept achieved by allusion can illustrate cultural beliefs and aspects through the literature. English and Uzbek analysis showcase that allusion in both languages can make conceptual signs while analyzing literary texts.

Linguoculturemes are the signs that illustrate national cultural values and their sources are derived from different aspects of culture such as myths, proverbs, sayings, realia, religion, customs and traditions, outstanding people, images, literature and art. National values and cultural specificity that is represented by linguoculturemes are verbalized by several ways such as mythologemes, proverbs, sayings, quotations, aphorisms, allusion, anthroponyms, etc.

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